

Supplementary information

S1. Fabrication procedure

Figure S1 provides a comprehensive illustration of the methodology employed in the fabrication of the devices analyzed in this study, highlighting the key steps and materials involved throughout the process.

Conventional (CONV) devices were manufactured following the next sequence of steps: 1) front electrode metallization by thermal evaporation of an AuGe/Ni/Au stack with respective thicknesses of 85 nm / 25 nm / 100 nm, followed by gold electroplating up to approximately 5 μm ; 2) mesa etching of the device to remove the contact layer and define the active area; and 3) rear metallization by deposition of a 200 nm-thick gold layer forming the rear electrode and back mirror.

Passivated Emitter Rear Contact (PERC) devices were manufactured following the next sequence of steps: 1) rear passivation was performed as described in the main text, consisting of the deposition of an a-SiC_x:H (2 nm) / Al₂O₃ (50 nm) / a-SiC (45 nm) stack; 2) front electrode metallization identical to that of the CONV device; 3) localized rear contacts were created through the dielectric stack using a Laser-Fired Contacts (LFC) process; 4) a Cr/Au (5 nm / 200 nm) bilayer was deposited to complete the rear electrode; and 5) a final mesa etch defined the device area and removed the contact layer outside the active region. Further details can be found in the Methodology section in the main body of this work.

Figure S1 Manufacturing process step by step for both CONV (Panel A) and PERC (panel B) Ge TPV devices.

S2. Spectral properties of TPV cells and emitters

The optical reflectivity (R_λ) of the emitter and the TPV cells has been measured at room temperature across the relevant wavelength range using two complementary systems: 1) a Nicolet 6700 FTIR equipped with a PIKE integrating sphere for the infrared range (2–15 μm), and 2) a Cary 7000 spectrophotometer with a built-in integrating sphere and a multiple-detector setup for the UV–Vis–NIR range (0.2–2.5 μm). This combination ensures reliable reflectance measurements across a broad wavelength spectrum.

Figure S2 presents the reflectance of the TPV cells obtained by merging the data from both setups previously mentioned, along with data reported in the literature for similar devices using spectrophotometers [1], [2]. For reference, the emission spectrum of the graphite emitter at the maximum operating temperature employed in the TPV experiments is shown.

Figure S2 Reflectivity spectra of the Ge-based TPV devices measured using two different instruments: an FTIR spectrometer equipped with an integrating sphere and a UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer. For each individual device (CONV and PERC), the spectra obtained with both instruments show an almost perfect overlap in the common spectral range, with deviations below 1% between 2.2 and 2.4 μm , confirming the excellent reproducibility of the measurements. For comparison, experimental reflectivity data from Fernández et al. [2], [3] are shown up to 2.5 μm , along with the calculated reflectivity presented from Martín et al. [1]. The emission spectrum of the graphite emitter at its maximum recorded temperature is also included for reference.

Both CONV and PERC devices developed in this work exhibit nearly identical spectral reflectivity, with only a slight improvement for the PERC device at wavelengths below 4 μm . This behavior arises because the effectiveness of the dielectric rear mirror is ultimately limited by strong FCA in the highly doped substrate [1], [4]. As a consequence, the optical benefit provided by the dielectric mirror is reduced to less than a 3 % of absolute value and confined to the short-wavelength region ($<4 \mu\text{m}$).

Similar FCA-limited behavior is also observed in the devices reported by Martín et al. [1] and Fernández et al. [2], as shown in Figure S2. In the latter case, the incorporation of an anti-reflection coating (ARC) significantly enhances absorption in the IB region ($<1.8 \mu\text{m}$), at the expense of reduced reflectivity in the OOB region. In both studies, oscillations within the IB region are evident, originating from Fabry–Pérot cavity effects associated with the GaAs layer in Martín’s structure and with the combined action of the ARC and GaInP layers in Fernández’s device.

Fernández et al. report experimental reflectivity measurements of the complete device only up to 2.5 μm , without extending the spectrum through optical simulations. In

contrast, Martín *et al.* measured the reflectivity of two separate surfaces: the active area without metal and a fully metallized surface using the front-electrode stack [1]. These measurements, also limited to 2.5 μm , were subsequently fitted using a transfer-matrix method (TMM) to extrapolate the optical response beyond the measured range. The reflectivity of the complete device was then reconstructed as a weighted combination of the experimentally measured metallized reflectivity and the TMM-adjusted response of the active area, accounting for the device shadowing factor (SF). This reconstructed reflectivity is the one reported in [1] and Figure S2, and is calculated using the following expression:

$$R_{device} = R_{metal} \cdot SF + R_{Active\ area} \cdot (1 - SF) \quad (1)$$

To complete the optical description required for the TPV analysis, the spectral emissivity of the thermal emitters considered in this work is examined next. Figure S3 shows the spectral emissivity, i.e. $1 - R_\lambda$, of the two emitters presented and analyzed in this work: 1) the graphite emitter used during the experiments, measured using both FTIR and spectrophotometer (as mentioned above), and 2) the calculated AlN/W spectrally selective emitter presented in [5] and used in [1] for TPV efficiency predictions.

Figure S3 Emissivity spectra, calculated using room temperature reflectivity data as $1 - R$, of the graphite emitter used in our TPV setup, compared with the emissivity simulated for a AlN/W emitter and used in Martín *et al.* device [1].

With the spectral properties of both the TPV devices and the thermal emitters established, we next assess their combined impact on the spectral efficiency of the system. Figure S4 shows the spectral efficiency (SE) as a function of emitter temperature for the CONV, PERC, and Martín *et al.* devices, evaluated using the two emitters described in Figure S3. Two emitter scenarios are considered: a broadband graphite emitter and an idealized spectrally selective AlN/W emitter. The SE is defined as the fraction of the absorbed radiative power lying above the TPV cell bandgap wavelength, λ_g , thereby quantifying the effect of emitter spectral selectivity on the usable radiation, following the definition introduced in [6]:

$$SE = \frac{\int_0^{\lambda_g} \varepsilon_{eff} P_{BB}(T_e, \lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} \varepsilon_{eff} P_{BB}(T_e, \lambda) d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

Here, λ_g is the TPV cell bandgap wavelength, $P_{BB}(T_e, \lambda)$ denotes the blackbody spectral power density of the emitter at temperature T_e , and $\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}(\lambda)$ accounts for the effective radiative coupling between the emitter and the cell.

For both emitter types, all devices exhibit nearly identical SE trends, highlighting that the achievable spectral efficiency is largely constrained by FCA absorption in the highly doped Ge substrate rather than by the rear-side optical design. The selective emitter significantly enhances SE compared to the graphite case, particularly at high emitter temperatures.

Figure S4 Spectral efficiency (SE) as a function of the emitter temperature for CONV, PERC, and Martin et al. devices, calculated for two different emitter scenarios: a broadband graphite emitter (solid lines) and a spectrally selective AlN/W emitter (dashed lines). Colors indicate the device architecture.

S3. Quantum efficiency (QE)

The internal quantum efficiency (IQE) of the CONV device shown in Figure S5 is obtained through EQE and in-situ reflectivity measurements on a dedicated finger-free test cell, fabricated from the same wafer as the final CONV device later characterized under TPV conditions. These measurements were carried out using a custom-built EQE setup at IES-UPM, based on a W lamp coupled with a grating monochromator and lock-in detection, with a reference Ge photodetector used to monitor and correct lamp intensity fluctuations, the same one used in [1].

Subsequently, the global reflectivity of the final CONV device, including the front metal grid, was measured using an integrating sphere. The EQE of the CONV device was then reconstructed by combining the IQE obtained from the finger-free device with the global reflectivity of the gridded device, according to

$$EQE(\lambda) = IQE(\lambda) (1 - R(\lambda)) \quad (3)$$

where $R(\lambda)$ is the global reflectivity of the final (gridded) CONV device.

For the PERC device, a different methodology was required because a finger-free dedicated cell was not available. In this case, EQE measurements were performed directly on the final (gridded) PERC cell using a commercial Oriel IQE 200 system, covering a spectral range from 300 to 1800 nm. Notably, these EQE measurements were acquired at a single angle of incidence, and the presence of (thick) front-side metal fingers is expected to significantly influence the measured response. To account for this effect, a correction

offset was introduced. This offset was determined by comparing the EQE of the CONV device reconstructed using the method described above with the corresponding EQE measured directly using the Oriel system. The resulting offset was then applied to the Oriel-measured EQE of the PERC device to obtain its equivalent EQE. Finally, combining this reconstructed EQE with the integrating-sphere reflectivity of the PERC device enabled the determination of the corresponding IQE of the PERC structure, which is also presented in Figure S5.

It is worth noting that these reconstructed IQE curves will be used only for the TPV model, and therefore, will only impact on the recalculation of the emitter temperatures used in the TPV efficiency analysis. Consequently, they do not influence on the reported experimental efficiencies in this work.

Figure S5 The plot compares the spectral response of our Ge-based TPV devices, showing both the reconstructed external quantum efficiency (EQE) of each cell and their internal quantum efficiency (IQE). Overlaid as a dashed curve is the spectral irradiance of the graphite emitter at 1496 °C, providing context for the TPV operating spectrum.

As shown in Figure S5, both CONV and PERC devices exhibit nearly identical EQE spectra, consistent with their identical front-side structures and differing only in rear passivation. Minor deviations observed above 1600 nm may be associated with differences in the passivation stack; however, the strong FCA discussed in the main text largely mask such effects. Due to this strong FCA, potential enhancements arising from the rear structure are not directly visible in the EQE, explaining the nearly identical response of both devices.

When compared with the state of the art, Figure S5A shows that Fernández et al. [2] reported significantly higher EQE, primarily due to the presence of an ARC. Moreover, our structures do not present the Fabry–Pérot oscillations reported by Martin et al. [1], which originate from the presence of a GaAs window layer in their structures. The elimination of the GaAs window layer in our devices enhances the EQE at shorter wavelengths (below 0.8 μm). While this spectral region is less relevant for operation at moderate/low emitter temperatures (e.g. < 1500 °C), it may become advantageous at higher emitter temperatures. For wavelengths above 0.8 μm, our EQE is lower than that reported by Martin et al. [1], mainly due to the higher SF and the absence of the GaAs window layer which behaves as an antireflecting coating, tuning the big EQE oscillation around 1.2 μm. Therefore, in both cases, the higher EQE of previous state of the art devices arises either from a significantly lower SF (6% versus 19% in our devices) or from the presence of an ARC.

It should be noted that the reported experimental data from Martin et al. in [1] correspond to a device characterized without front metal shading. To enable a fair comparison at the device level, the EQE plotted in Figure S5A is calculated as:

$$EQE_{device}(\lambda) = EQE_{active\ area}(\lambda) \cdot (1 - SF) \quad (4)$$

where EQE_{active} refers to the metal-free active-area and EQE_{device} to the device with the corresponding SF.

S4. Dark I-V characteristics

The dark I-V characteristics of the two devices under study are presented in Figure S6. Each I-V curve was fitted using the single-diode model at 25 °C to extract key parameters: the saturation current density (J_0), ideality factor (n), and shunt resistance (R_{sh}). The series resistance (R_s) extracted from the dark IV fitting was not used in the TPV cell model. This is because the current paths in dark conditions are not equal to those in illumination induced by intense irradiance. Instead, the series resistance used in the model was derived from the fitting of the illuminated $I-V$ curves obtained in the flash measurements [7], following the method described in [8], which better represent the real behaviour of the devices under high-power operation. All extracted parameters are summarized in Table S1 .

Figure S6 Dark IV response of the devices reported

A notably low shunt resistance was observed in the PERC device. This behavior is attributed to the removal of the GaAs contact layer after the mesa etching process, which induces a lateral etch in the perimeter of the cell that creates leakage current paths. This hypothesis is supported by the fact that initial electrical measurements performed prior to this etch yielded shunt resistance values above 10 $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$, two orders of magnitude greater than the value recorded after the etch (Table S1). Therefore, low shunt resistances can be simply avoided by removing the GaAs layer before the mesa etch.

Nevertheless, this limitation becomes less critical under actual operating conditions. Given the high current densities expected during TPV operation, the impact of a low shunt resistance is significantly mitigated. In such regimes, the current flowing through the shunt path is negligible compared to the total photocurrent, thereby minimizing its effect on overall device performance.

Table S1 Results of the fitting procedure applied to the reported experimental data.

	Cell area (cm^2) ⁱ	J_0 [A/cm^2]	n	R_{sh} [Ωcm^2]	R_s [$\text{m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$]
Fernandez et al [2]	1.55 ⁱⁱ	1.8e-6	1	-	23
Martin et al [1]	0.096	1.6e-6	1	-	1
CONV	1.05	1.83e-06	1	>100	7.67
PERC	1.05	1.85e-06	1	193.5	17.69

ⁱ Defined as area inside the mesa.

ⁱⁱ Only the active area is reported, excluding the busbars.

S5. I-V characteristics under flash test conditions

The TPV cells have been characterized using the constant-voltage I - V curve flash tester HELIOS 3198 [9]. In this method, the cells are biased at a fixed voltage and exposed to multiple light pulses, allowing the system to record the current generated during the flash decay. By repeating the procedure at different bias voltages, a family of I - V curves corresponding to various irradiance levels is obtained. This system thus enables the acquisition of I - V curves under variable irradiance conditions.

Figure S7 shows the measured J - V curves together with their corresponding fits to the single-diode circuit model. In this figure, the area used for converting current (I) to current density (J) is 0.85 cm^2 , corresponding to the active area including the metal fingers but excluding the busbars. A simultaneous fitting of all J - V curves, obtained under different irradiance conditions, was performed using a multi-curve fitting approach described in [8]. This method captures the device response across a broad range of current densities and voltages, ensuring that the extracted parameters more accurately represent the actual operational regime compared to single-point or low-irradiance fittings.

Figure S7 Fitting of multiple illuminated JV curves for the CONV (left) and PERC (right) devices using the flash setup. The current density was normalized to the active area excluding the busbar, giving an active area of 0.85 cm^2 .

Notably, the extracted J_0 from this fitting (shown in the inset of the figure) is consistent with the value obtained from dark J - V curve fitting (Section S4), thereby reinforcing the validity of the results.

Figure S8 presents the key parameters V_{oc} versus J_{sc} (panel A) and FF versus J_{sc} (panel B), extracted from the results in Figure S7, for the two cells developed in this work, together with previously reported data by Fernandez et. al. [2], [3] and Martin et. al. [1], [2]. The figure also includes the results of the single-diode model obtained from the fitted parameters.

Figure S8 High-irradiance characterization of our TPV cells under flash-test or laser illumination in the case of Martin et al (non-TPV conditions). (A) J_{sc} versus V_{oc} with single-diode dark-IV fits, confirming the superposition principle. (B) Fill factor versus J_{sc} , overlaid with single-diode model predictions computed at 25 °C using device-specific R_s , R_{sh} , and J_0 ; shaded bands denote $\pm 1\%$. The data noted by the arrows corresponds to the active area excluding the busbars.

S6. Calorimetric characterization and model fitting of TPV cells

This section presents the experimental results obtained from the calorimetric setup [10], which was used to measure the electrical and thermal power outputs of the TPV cells under operating conditions, together with the corresponding model results and fit parameters.

Table S2 and Table S3 Summary of PERC data in the experimental TPV setup. The temperature values in brackets correspond to the experimental measurements obtained through our TPV setup, while the others represent the corrected values using the method described in Section 2.3. Same considerations as explained in Table S3.

Table S3 summarize the relevant parameters (temperature, I_{sc} , V_{oc} , I_{mpp} , V_{mpp}) for the CONV and PERC cells, respectively, along with their output power (P_{mpp}) and dissipated heat (Q_{dis}). These values are then used to determine the TPV conversion efficiency through the following equation:

$$\eta_{TPV} = \frac{P_{mpp}}{P_{mpp} + Q_{dis}} \quad (5)$$

Both uncorrected values (reported in brackets) and corrected values for the emitter and cell temperatures are included. As explained in Section 2.3, the temperature correction relies on two factors, r_e and r_c , introduced to improve the agreement between the experimental results and the model. The optimal correction factors that provide the best fit are summarized in Table S4.

In addition, Table S2 and Table S3 report the saturation current density, J_0 , obtained from fitting the single-diode model to the $I-V$ curves measured under different TPV operating conditions (emitter temperatures). The fitted curves are shown in Figure S9 for the CONV

(panel A) and PERC (panel B) cells. A clear increase in J_0 with increasing emitter temperature is observed, which is attributed to the corresponding rise in cell temperature.

Table S2 Summary of CONV data measured under the experimental TPV setup. Temperatures shown in brackets correspond to the values directly measured by a thermocouple located in the calorimeter, a few millimeters away from the cell. Thermal grease is used between the copper components of the setup, while a thermally conductive epoxy ensures the bonding between the cell and the copper pedestal. The remaining temperatures correspond to corrected values obtained using the procedure described in Section 2.3, which accounts for thermal resistances in the mounting stack and for temperature gradients across the Ge substrate, leading to a higher effective p–n junction temperature and influencing the extracted J_0 .

$T_{emitter}$ [°C]	T_{cell} [°C]	I_{sc} [A]	V_{oc} [mV]	I_{mpp} [A]	V_{mpp} [mV]	P_{mpp} [W]	TPV efficiency [%]	Q [W]	FF [%]	J_0 [A/cm ²]
956 (980)	27.7 (26.9)	0.25	307.94	0.23	243.93	0.06	1.90	2.84	71.62	1.72E-06
1041 (1073)	27.9 (26.9)	0.42	321.16	0.39	253.19	0.10	2.66	3.64	72.36	1.75E-06
1113 (1155)	28.1 (26.9)	0.65	331.22	0.60	262.56	0.16	3.41	4.47	72.79	1.79E-06
1211 (1267)	28.5 (26.9)	1.08	342.50	1.00	271.77	0.27	4.44	5.82	72.83	1.91E-06
1293 (1366)	29.0 (27.1)	1.61	350.61	1.45	281.14	0.41	5.36	7.22	72.48	2.07E-06
1364 (1455)	29.5 (27.2)	2.21	356.89	2.02	281.08	0.57	6.13	8.67	71.70	2.25E-06
1425 (1535)	29.8 (27.1)	2.88	361.73	2.61	281.01	0.73	6.74	10.15	70.64	2.44E-06
1462 (1586)	30.4 (27.4)	3.38	363.89	3.00	285.14	0.86	7.16	11.18	69.65	2.62E-06
1480 (1610)	31.1 (27.9)	3.64	364.14	3.32	275.79	0.92	7.29	11.70	69.11	2.83E-06

Table S3 Summary of PERC data in the experimental TPV setup. The temperature values in brackets correspond to the experimental measurements obtained through our TPV setup, while the others represent the corrected values using the method described in Section 2.3. Same considerations as explained in Table S3.

$T_{emitter}$ [°C]	T_{cell} [°C]	I_{sc} [A]	V_{oc} [mV]	I_{mpp} [A]	V_{mpp} [mV]	P_{mpp} [W]	TPV efficiency [%]	Q [W]	FF [%]	J_0 [A/cm ²]
920 (952)	25.2 (24.8)	0.18	296.64	0.16	230.75	0.04	1.89	1.92	68.79	1.79E-06
1002 (1045)	25.4 (24.9)	0.32	308.57	0.28	244.02	0.07	2.61	2.55	69.95	1.90E-06
1073 (1128)	25.7 (25.0)	0.49	316.99	0.43	251.82	0.11	3.27	3.23	70.24	2.13E-06
1153 (1226)	26.0 (25.1)	0.78	324.45	0.70	251.83	0.18	4.04	4.17	69.57	2.53E-06
1238 (1336)	26.2 (25.1)	1.23	330.17	1.11	251.44	0.28	4.87	5.41	68.39	3.21E-06
1309 (1434)	26.6 (25.2)	1.76	332.78	1.56	251.43	0.39	5.52	6.70	66.95	4.16E-06
1372 (1528)	27.1 (25.4)	2.39	333.20	2.12	243.99	0.52	5.98	8.11	64.68	5.59E-06
1426 (1617)	27.6 (25.6)	3.13	331.76	2.74	236.60	0.65	6.30	9.63	62.33	7.81E-06

Table S4 Fitting parameters for the correction of temperatures measured in the TPV calorimetric set up.

Device	r_c [°C/W]	r_e [°C/W]
CONV	0.27	4.06
PERC	0.22	5.67

Figure S9. IV curves obtained during the TPV characterization. Panel (A) corresponds to the CONV cell, and panel (B) to the PERC cell. In both cases, the experimental data are shown together with the corresponding fits obtained using our model, as well as the emitter temperatures that best reproduce the experimental.

S7. Electrodes design and series resistance analysis

This section analyses the contribution of the different resistivity sources to the total series resistance of the device. Three main contributions are considered, namely: the front contact, the bulk and the rear contact:

$$R_s = R_{front} + R_{Bulk} + R_{Rear} \quad (6)$$

The front contact contribution (R_{front}) which is common to both CONV and PERC architectures, is evaluated using the analytical lumped-element model described in [11]. Within this framework, the front resistance can be expressed as the sum of three components and their corresponding contributions:

$$R_{front} = R_{me} + R_{le} + R_{ce} \quad (7)$$

where the individual terms are given by:

$$R_{me} = \frac{dl^2\rho_m}{12wb} \quad (8)$$

$$R_{le} = \frac{d^2R_{\square}}{12} \quad (9)$$

$$R_{ce} = \frac{\rho_{ce}}{(w/b)} \quad (10)$$

- R_{front} is the total front-side series resistance contribution.
- R_{me} is the resistance associated with current transport along the front metal grid fingers.
- R_{le} is the lateral carrier transport resistance in the emitter between adjacent grid fingers.
- R_{ce} is the metal–semiconductor contact resistance at the front interface.

The geometrical and material parameters are defined as follows:

- d is the pitch between adjacent front metal fingers.
- w is the width of the front metal fingers.
- l is the effective finger length, defined by the active cell width minus the busbar regions.
- b is the thickness of the front metal fingers.
- ρ_m is the electrical resistivity of the front metal.
- R_{\square} is the sheet resistance of the emitter layer.
- ρ_{ce} is the specific contact resistivity of the metal–semiconductor interface at the front contact.

A schematic illustration of these contributions and their physical origin is provided in Figure S10.

Figure S10. (A) Schematic cross-section of the CONV device architecture, indicating the relevant geometrical dimensions and the parameters of the front metal grid used in the resistance modeling. (B) Schematic cross-section of the PERC device architecture, showing the same front-grid geometrical parameters together with the additional rear-contact geometry.

The bulk contribution (R_{bulk}) is calculated in a different way for both CONV and PERC devices. For CONV cells, the bulk contribution is simply obtained by multiplying the bulk resistivity ($\rho = 3.36 \times 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, value extracted from [12], [13]) by the wafer thickness:

$$R_{\text{bulk,CONV}} = \rho w \quad (11)$$

In the case of the PERC device, the calculation must account for a more complex 3D distribution of the current towards the punctual contacts in the rear side. For that, we use the analytical approach described in detail in [14], [15], [16], according to which the bulk contribution of a PERC device is given by:

$$R_{\text{bulk,PERC}} = P^2 \cdot \frac{\rho \cdot r}{2} \arctan\left(\frac{2 \cdot w}{r}\right) + \rho \cdot w \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{w}{P}\right)}\right) \quad (12)$$

where P is the pitch between contact points (arranged in a square pattern), ρ is the substrate resistivity, r is the contact radius, and w is the wafer thickness. The first term represents the spreading resistance (R_{spread}) associated with current converging into isolated point contacts in the large-pitch limit. The second term is an exponential interpolation (R_{int}) term that captures the transition towards the dense-contact regime ($P \ll w$), in which the rear surface behaves increasingly like a fully metallized back contact.

Finally, the rear contact resistance (R_{rear}) is obtained for both PERC and CONV devices such as:

$$R_{\text{rear}} = \frac{\rho_c}{f_c} \quad (13)$$

where ρ_c is the specific contact resistance, and f_c is a contact coverage parameter. This parameter is equal to unity for CONV devices, reflecting full rear-contact coverage, whereas for PERC devices it corresponds to the fraction of laser-processed area, given by $f_c = \pi r^2 / P^2$.

For convenience, we define the LFC resistance of the PERC device as the addition of bulk and rear contact resistances:

$$R_{LFC}[\Omega\text{cm}^2] = \frac{\rho_c}{f_c} + R_{bulk,PERC} \quad (14)$$

Figure S11 summarizes the resistance components required to calculate the total series resistance according to equations (6)– (7). Each quantity is shown in a dedicated panel: the electroplated front-metal resistivity ρ_m (panel A), the emitter sheet resistance R_{\square} (panel B), the front metal–semiconductor specific contact resistivity ρ_{ce} (panel C), and the rear contact resistance R_{rear} (panel D). The reported values were extracted from Transfer Line Method (TLM) measurements (B, C and D) and metal-layer sheet resistance characterization (A). Measurements were performed on multiple devices, leading to the statistical dispersion reflected in the box plots. These experimentally determined parameters are subsequently used as inputs for the series-resistance modelling of both CONV and PERC architectures.

Figure S11. (A) Electrical resistivity of electroplated Au as a function of annealing temperature and stirring conditions. (B) Sheet resistance of the GaInP window layer. (C) Specific contact resistivity ρ_{ce} of the front metal contact as a function of annealing temperature. (D) Rear contact resistance of Au contacts on $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ doped Ge substrates.

The specific contact resistivity (ρ_c) of the rear contact on for the PERC devices was not directly measured experimentally. Instead, it was inferred from the total series resistance measured for the PERC device and the calculated front contact contribution (obtained as the sum of its individual components using the experimentally determined parameters reported). Subtracting the calculated front contribution from the total series resistance yields a value of $3.5 \text{ m}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ associated with the rear contact and substrate, which corresponds to a ρ_c of $5.1 \cdot 10^{-5} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$, following equation (14). This value is in line with the ρ_c of $5.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ reported in [15] for laser-fired point contacts using aluminum as the contact metal.

Contact design and series resistance of optimized devices:

Using the empirical values for each resistive contribution summarized previously and the corresponding analytical expressions, the geometrical parameters of the front and rear contacts were optimized. Figure S12A shows a two-dimensional map of the front-grid contribution to the series resistance as a function of finger width w and finger pitch d . This map was used to identify geometries that minimize R_{front} while maintaining a practical shading factor ($SF = w/d$), thereby locating an equilibrium between electrical optimum and fabrication constraints. The experimental point on the graphs corresponds to the fabricated CONV device for reference.

Figure S12. A) Two-dimensional map of the front-grid contribution to the series resistance as a function of finger width w and finger pitch d , including iso-resistance contours. B) Corresponding map of the simulated electrical power ratio relative to the ideal case ($R_s=0$, $SF=0$), illustrating the impact of front-grid geometry on electrical performance. In both A) and B), the experimental design point for CONV devices is indicated for reference. C) Rear laser-fired contact resistance R_{LFC} as a function of the processed rear area fraction f_c , obtained from the analytical model. The total resistance is shown together with the separate contributions from the contact term ρ_c/f_c , the spreading resistance R_{spread} , and the interaction term R_{int} , as defined in Eqs. (10) and (12). The experimental result is highlighted for reference.

Figure S12B translates the same (d, w) design space into a performance-oriented metric by reporting the simulated maximum-power ratio relative to an ideal reference case with $SF = 0$ and $R_s = 0$ at the case of an emitting temperature of 1500 °C. The simulations include the geometry-dependent front-grid series resistance together with fixed bulk and rear-contact contributions common to all (d, w) configurations. Shading was treated spectrally by combining the measured reflectivity of the Au front metal with the measured reflectivity of the CONV device ($SF \approx 19\%$) to reconstruct the active-area response and derive a geometry-dependent EQE (and therefore J_{sc}) for each (d, w) pair. In this way, Figure S12B highlights the trade-off between reducing the front-grid series resistance (favoring denser and/or wider grids) and limiting shading losses (favoring sparser and/or

narrower grids), enabling the identification of grid geometries that maximize deliverable power under TPV operation.

Importantly, this optimization does not yield a single unique solution, but rather a broad region of grid geometry providing comparable electrical performance. This tolerance allows practical fabrication considerations to guide the final choice. The systematic widening of the fingers observed after fabrication—caused by photoresist profile evolution and metal electroplating—is an intrinsic feature of the process and occurs for all devices, independently of the nominal mask design. As a result, although the photomask defined a nominal finger width of $15\ \mu\text{m}$, the effective width in the fabricated devices is approximately $19\ \mu\text{m}$. This effect must be considered in the design process and find a way to minimize it during fabrication.

Figure S12C shows the R_{LFC} contribution of the PERC device as a function of the processed area fraction of f_c . Increasing f_c reduces R_{LFC} by shortening the current-spreading path; however, it simultaneously increases the disruption of the rear mirror, leading to a degradation of its optical reflectivity and, consequently, of the overall optical performance. This trade-off between electrical resistance and rear-side reflectivity has been quantitatively analyzed in previous studies on laser-fired contacts, where an optimal contact pitch was identified to balance both effects [15]. Following this established approach, an intermediate processed fraction of approximately 2.1 %, corresponding a pitch of $P \approx 60\ \mu\text{m}$, is selected in this work, providing sufficiently low series resistance while largely preserving the optical quality of the rear mirror.

Taken together, the analyses presented in Figure S13 enable the experimental results to be interpreted in terms of contact geometry and scaling effects. The resistance model assembled from the experimentally extracted contributions shows good agreement with the measured values across different devices, supporting its use as a consistent framework for the analysis that follows. The Figure S13 summarizes how front-grid geometry, rear-contact processing, and device scaling translate into the total series resistance for different device architectures, assuming a two-busbar configuration with fixed busbar dimensions and edge-to-contact tolerances. Importantly, when increasing the device area, the front-grid layout is not re-optimized. Instead, key geometrical and material parameters, such as finger width, finger pitch, metal thickness, busbar geometry, and contact resistivities, are kept constant. This approach focuses on the effect of device scaling on the series-resistance budget, without introducing additional grid re-optimization effects.

Figure S13 (A) CONV device as fabricated (C) PERC device as fabricated.

As observed, in the as-fabricated device in Figure S13 the bottleneck of the series resistance is located at the front contact, arising either from the R_{ce} or from the finite R_{me} . The rear contact contribution, despite it being less relevant in both devices, is more significant in PERC devices. This is mostly attributed to the lower f_c , which makes the impact of ρ_c more noticeable.

The relatively high front contact resistance in both PERC and CONV devices ($R_{ce}=6.4\times 10^{-4}\ \Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$) originates from the unannealed metal (AuGe/Ni/Au)/semiconductor interface. Although this contact resistance can, in principle, be further reduced through post-deposition annealing, all annealing attempts resulted in short-circuiting devices. This behavior is attributed to the thin GaAs contact layer, which is insufficient to prevent metal spike penetration into the p–n junction during annealing. Such penetration ultimately leads to severe leakage current paths and device failure.

The R_{me} greatly depends on the conductivity of the electroplated gold layer, which is primarily determined by the electroplating conditions. For instance, increasing electrolyte agitation during deposition promotes a denser and more uniform gold layer, thereby improving its conductivity and reducing resistive losses. The degree of agitation depends on the stirrer and the configuration of the plating setup; the key indicator of proper mixing is the formation of a visible vortex in the electrolyte. Because of the fabrication sequence and the learning curve associated with the process, this optimization was not implemented in the present PERC device, which explains the higher series resistance of this device. However, it represents a viable strategy to enhance device performance.

Projecting series resistance for scaled up and scaled down scenarios:

According to the previous discussion there are three main strategies for reducing the front-side contact series resistance: (i) annealing to improve the front specific contact resistivity, (ii) increasing the thickness of the GaAs contact layer to prevent short-circuiting of the pn junction, and (iii) optimizing the electroplating process to enhance gold conductivity. Based on this, Figure S14 presents a comparative analysis of the series resistance as a function of the area for both device architectures, along with a scaled-down configuration to reproduce the work of Martin et al [1].

In this figure, panels A, B, and C show the contribution of the series resistance R_s as a function of the total device area, assuming a square layout and keeping the finger width (w) at 15 μm and the spacing (d) at 100 μm . This configuration represents the design choice for the scaled-up device (total device area of 1.05 cm^2). In this analysis, the total device area is used as the scaling parameter on the horizontal axis, while the busbar dimensions and edge margins are kept constant. Consequently, the electrically active area is slightly smaller than the total device area but scales proportionally with it.

In panels D, E, and F, the cell remains square, but the finger width is reduced to 6 μm and the spacing to 94 μm , representing the design choice for the scaled-down configuration (total device area of 0.096 cm^2). Using the total device area as the scaling parameter ensures a consistent comparison of the resistive contributions across device sizes while preserving realistic contact layouts and fixed peripheral regions.

The Figure S14 shows that, once the front contact is improved through annealing (e.g. panel C), the bottleneck in PERC devices shifts to the rear side of the cell, mainly due to the relatively small, contacted area.

These calculations are subsequently employed in Section 4.1 of the main text, where the TPV model described above is applied to estimate the projected conversion efficiencies

under two representative operating scenarios. The first scenario considers large-area devices operating with non-selective emitters, such as graphite, which are relevant for practical high-power implementations. The second scenario focuses on smaller devices combined with spectrally selective emitters, where enhanced photon management can be exploited to improve efficiency. Building on these two cases, the analysis is further extended to explore potential performance improvements by systematically maximizing the achievable efficiency within the constraints imposed by the proposed geometries. In this way, the calculations do not merely reproduce measured behavior but provide a consistent framework to assess the performance limits and optimization pathways of Ge-based TPV devices under realistic and idealized operating conditions.

Figure S14 (A) CONV device after the annealing treatment; (B) CONV device downscaled to the Martin *et al.* form factor; (C) PERC device after the annealing treatment; (D) PERC device downscaled to the Martin *et al.* form factor; (E) Martin *et al.* device scaled to our form factor; and (F) Martin *et al.* device as reported in [1]. For the rear contact in the PERC devices, the processed area fraction f_c is defined by the laser-fired contact pitch, which is fixed to $60 \mu\text{m}$ in all cases, corresponding to the value implemented in the fabricated devices.

S8. Key Assumptions Behind Reported State-of-the-Art Ge TPV Cell Results

In this section, we provide a detailed analysis of the reported data from two reference works (Fernández *et al.* [2] and Martin *et al.* [1]) that are discussed throughout this study.

The work by Fernández *et al.* [2], [3] reflects an early semi-empirical approach used by the TPV community to estimate device performance before calorimetric experimental setups became more popular. First, the reflectivity spectrum is experimentally reported only between 0.2 and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$, omitting longer wavelengths that are essential for TPV applications. Second, no optical cavity is considered, and the view factor is simply assumed to be 1. Finally, and most importantly, the calculations assume a microstructured tungsten emitter heated to $1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and with spectral cut-off, i.e. zero emissivity beyond $1.88 \mu\text{m}$ (the indirect bandgap of germanium). Therefore, the work neglects optical losses in the sub-bandgap region. While useful for providing a quick estimation of the ultimate

efficiency potential, this idealization leads to inflated efficiency values that overlook long-wavelength thermal radiation and real optical behavior. The reported TPV efficiency of 16.5 % is calculated analytically using the standard PV efficiency relation:

$$\eta_{TPV} = \frac{I_{sc}V_{oc}FF}{P_{TPV}} \quad (15)$$

with I_{sc} , V_{oc} , and FF taken from the I-V curve, and P_{TPV} estimated from the truncated emission spectrum of a micro-structured wolfram emitter, as explained above. The assumption of perfect reflectivity beyond the cut-off wavelength artificially reduces the absorbed power, again leading to an overestimated efficiency figure.

Martin et al. [1] follow a more refined but still semi-empirical methodology, motivated by the same lack of calorimetric TPV measurement setups. The most relevant assumption regards the use of a simulated spectrally selective emitter, inspired from the work of [5] and reproduced using TMM. The emitter emissivity is purely simulated and lacks experimental optical validation at TPV operating temperatures, with its thermal stability inferred from literature data (AlN/W reported to be stable ex situ up to ~ 1700 °C, while AlN is expected to decompose above ~ 1500 °C under high-vacuum conditions). Accordingly, the emissivity adopted in [1] should be regarded as an idealized, simulation-based spectrum rather than an experimentally validated emitter response.

Moreover, in Martin et al. [1], the cell reflectance is not obtained from direct global measurements of the final metallized device. Instead, optical characterization is performed on a reference device without front metallization, for which the EQE and reflectance of the active area are measured directly. In a second step, the optical response of the front metal is measured independently on a separate metal film. The device-level optical response is then reconstructed by combining the measured reflectance of the metal-covered regions with that of the optically active semiconductor area using a geometrical model based on the SF. Specifically, the EQE of the device is obtained by scaling the EQE of the active area by the unshaded fraction, following Equation (4), while the effective reflectance is calculated as an area-weighted combination of the metal and semiconductor contributions as in Equation (1). This approach enables the reconstruction of the effective EQE and reflectance of the metallized TPV device without direct global optical measurements.

The use of small-area devices for electrical characterization significantly reduces the impact of series resistance, particularly contributions associated with front-grid geometry, as discussed in the previous section. This facilitates electrical measurements under high current densities and allows the device to operate closer to its ideal electrical behavior. However, the resulting electrical performance is not directly representative of larger-area TPV devices operating under practical high-irradiance conditions, where series resistance and front-grid design play a much more critical role.

The overall TPV efficiency is estimated using the oversimplified expression $\eta_{TPV} = P_{mpp}/(VF \cdot (P_{emitted} - P_{reflected}))$, where VF is the view factor, $P_{emitted}$ denotes the emitted spectrum in vacuum, and $P_{reflected}$ is obtained by multiplying $P_{emitted}$ by the cell reflectance. However, this formulation provides only a crude estimate of the net radiative power absorbed by the cell, as it neglects the complex radiative exchange between the emitter and the photovoltaic cell. A more accurate description requires the use of an

effective emissivity, as adopted in this work, or alternatively, full ray-tracing simulations. This simplification becomes particularly problematic for emitters with low emissivity—such as the emitter considered in their study—because radiation reflected by the cell is not efficiently reabsorbed but instead undergoes multiple reflections at the emitter, leading to a significant misestimation of the absorbed power.

Overall, both approaches provide estimations of TPV efficiency that rely heavily on important assumptions. These include truncated or simulated spectral data, simplified geometries, and analytical corrections for reflection and shadowing. Such assumptions must be carefully considered when comparing with directly measured efficiencies.

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